

The accuracy vs. interpretability trade-off in Fraud Detection Model

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KEYWORDS: Fraud Detection, Unbalanced Data, Data Analysis, Interpretability, Metrics, Human Data Mediation.

Abstract

Like a hydra, fraudsters adapt and circumvent increasingly sophisticated barriers, erected in particular by banking institutions that must quickly take measures to avoid losses while guaranteeing the satisfaction of customers who do not fraud. Facing an expanding flow of operations, banks' efficiency relies on Data Analytics to support established risk control processes, but also on understanding the underlying fraud mechanism. In addition, since fraud can be a criminal act, there is no escaping the search for evidence. These legal, operational and strategic constraints lead to a trade-off on the means to be implemented for the fraud management. This paper first focuses on the translation of practical questions raised in the Banking industry at each step of the fraud management process into performance evaluation necessary to design a Fraud Detection Model. Second, it considers a fan of machine learning approaches addressing these specificities: the imbalance between fraudulent and non-fraudulent operations, the lack of fully trusted labels, the concept-drift phenomenon and the unavoidable trade-off between accuracy and explainability of the detection. This state of art sheds some light on a race for the best technology between black-box machine learning models improved by post-hoc interpretation and intrinsic interpretable models boosted to gain accuracy. Finally, it discusses how concrete and promising hybrid approaches can provide pragmatic, short-term responses to the needs of banks and policy makers without swallowing up stakeholders with economical and ethical stakes in a technological race.

INTRODUCTION

Like a hydra, fraudsters adapt and circumvent increasingly sophisticated barriers, erected in particular by banking institutions that must quickly take measures to avoid losses while guaranteeing the satisfaction of customers who do not fraud. Facing a growing flow of operations, banks' efficiency relies on Data Analytics to support established risk control processes, but also on understanding the underlying fraud mechanism. In addition, since fraud can be a criminal act, there is no escaping the search for evidence (Ryman-Tubb et al.,

2018). These legal, operational and strategic constraints lead to a trade-off on the means to be implemented for the fraud management. This paper first focuses on the practical questions raised by fraud management tasks and metrics specificities when building Fraud Detection Models (FDM) that address the trade-off between accuracy and explainability of the detection. Second, it provides a State Of The Art (SOTA) of the different Machine Learning based approaches to dealing with these data. Finally, it discusses how concrete approaches can provide pragmatic, short-term responses to the needs of banks and policy makers without swallowing up stakeholders with economical and ethical stakes in a technological race.

I- Fraud detection activities

The fraud management process is a flow of tasks, tainted by a level of human intervention and by economic issues, proper to the nature of the banking operations to control. It can't be reduced to a binary fraud detection automatic device, and the device has to be adapted to the specificities of the process, in particular in terms of metrics to optimize through an algorithmic approach. In this first part, we put in perspective the operational questions and needs in order to qualify the concept of performance dear to the modeling.

A. Overview of fraud types in banking industry

The fraud can be defined as all acts of cheating carried out by deceit and bad faith for the purpose of obtaining an advantage. Fraud has the effect of damaging an individual, a company, an association, the State, etc. Beyond the psychological and moral impacts (Alexopoulos et al., 2007), financial losses due to fraud represent a serious risk for private and public domains, such as tax collection, insurance, telecommunications or banking industry. This last sector is particularly aimed by the fraudsters as the volume of banking operations and the diversity of channels grow up. In view of the specific features of the banking sector and the various crises that have marked it over the last few decades, the Basel Commission identified from 2004 the fraud, and in particular external fraud, as a major operational risk. This risk then impacts the calculation of the minimum solvency ratio for banks (McDonough ratio), which is increasingly restrictive and is in the process of being standardized. Thus, the fraud subject remains of first importance for a banking company: fraud losses are not only suffered in the immediate term, but have consequences over time and are under close surveillance.

This supervision is often declined through the various banking products (credit or debit cards, cheques, private or corporate accounts, different types of loans, trading financial instruments...), by type of operations (transfers, payments, direct debit, deposits, money withdrawal...) or channels (physical network, ATM, paper documents, internet, mobile applications...), and by fraudster's finalities (money laundering, financing of terrorism, personal or organized gang enrichment...). These dimensions are strongly linked to local or national market specificities and trends, such as regulations, competition between banks and with new entrants, or customer behaviour patterns in terms of bank product consumption or

channel preferences. For example, OSMP reports¹ that the volume of online transactions is quickly rising, and customers require near instantaneous bank response, even for international payments, whereas cheques are slowly decreasing in volume, or have even disappeared in some countries, and can be treated with a longer delay of several hours. The capacity of a bank to satisfy specific customer needs and face competition are critical.

Beyond these business issues, each type of bank product, operation, channel and fraudster's finality can be characterized by its own data, internal (past operations, third party characteristics, internal processes or documents...) or external to the bank (fraudsters behaviour outside the bank or online, international blacklists, regulation and guidelines...), and the fraud detection devices face new challenges in terms of operation volumes growth, but also data diversity, especially when these dimensions have to be combined. In fact, the variety of banking services present a broadening panel of opportunities for this illegal activity, and each intersection or combination of dimensions can present its own sophisticated operation modes, including phishing, malwares, impersonation, payment theft or forgery, account takeover, etc. The diversity of these multi-dimensional and combined tactics (see Figure 1) is enhanced with a rapid and unpredictable change: fraudsters invent new approaches, test security and prevention barriers and quickly adapt. In this context, strong and dynamic fraud management is key for the banking industry.

Figure 1: Illustration of fraud dimensions

¹ Report 2018, Observatoire de la sécurité des moyens de paiement, https://www.banque-france.fr/sites/default/files/medias/documents/819172_osmp2018_web_3.pdf

B. Description of different tasks in fraud management

The global Fraud Management Lifecycle has been described (Wilhelm, 2004) as a set of seven steps: deterrence, prevention, detection, mitigation, analysis, policy, investigation and prosecution. With the pressure from regulators, customers and cost reduction objectives, the mitigation step has to be realized as quickly as possible without slowing down most of the usual operations. This acceleration of the process tends to break down the steps into automatable and human tasks, which can themselves be accelerated by appropriate devices. In the retail banking industry, the process can be simplified to a set of four main tasks (see Figure 2 below) linked to banking operations: **the alerting for operations at risk of fraud, the investigation of issued alerts, the action against suspected fraudsters, and the a posteriori fraud monitoring.**

Figure 2: Simplified process of fraud management

Task 1: Alerting

The first task is aimed at detecting as fast and precisely as possible a potentially fraudulent operation. Today, as most operations are too voluminous to be processed by hand, the main issue of the alerting is its automation in order to suspend or free the potential fraudulent operation without slowing down the usual operations. For most of them, such as cash withdrawal, credit card payments, check deposit, or online transfers, this task is usually automated as a set of fixed and manually adjustable business rules, and results in the

suspension of the operation and the issuing of an alert. However, the accuracy of these alerts for such rare events is often insufficient: the business filters are too tight (fraud passes through the barrier) or too loose (too many operations are suspended, creating customer risk and alert treatment charge).

Task 2: Investigation

The task of investigation, often carried out manually by the backoffice for each alert, leads to accept the operation despite the alert, or to confirm a suspicion of fraud. The major issue of this task is the acceleration of the human investigation process: the control has to concentrate on the riskier operations and quickly confirm the suspicion with explicit arguments, or, inversely, free rapidly less suspicious suspended operations. The fraud experts need for this task to have access to the right and interpretable information for each investigated operation in order to justify the suspicion and the resulting action. The task is strongly constrained by available human resources: the number of alerts that can be properly controlled is limited, and prioritization is very welcome.

Task 3: Action

Upon a suspicion, action must be taken against the potential fraudster: this third task is carried out by the bank or by the appropriate legal authority in order to quickly avoid or limit the impact of the fraud (financial loss, image...). The action can also be needed following the disclosure of a fraud on a transaction that has fallen through the cracks of the previous steps: in fact, most of the frauds are revealed once they succeeded, but the recorded loss can sometimes be retrieved (litigation, legal action) or recidivism prevented (customer account cancellation...). The action has not only to be ethically justified in terms of charges proving the fraud or a strong suspicion, but also in terms of consistency between the potential loss due to a given operation and the cost of the action and of the precedent tasks: in this context, costly action for numerous frauds with low impact is not acceptable. If this task remains manual, its constraints strongly impact the previous tasks, and some subtasks can appear to be good candidates for moving up the process to accelerate mitigation and avoid manual action.

Task 4: Monitoring

The fourth and final task requires post-hoc analysis to understand the evolution of fraudsters' behaviour and fraud management failures in order to better dissuade and prevent future frauds and to feed a process of continuous improvement of previous tasks: fine tuning the detection model, increasing productivity on the investigation and enhancing actions against the future fraudsters to limit the impact in terms of financial losses, moral and image prejudice for citizens and for banks. The main issue of this monitoring task, usually remaining manual, is to be flexible enough to adjust to bank product consumption and to capture the quickly changing fraud patterns, in particular when these patterns were not detected on time.

Other tasks

The other tasks related to the FDM consist of usual operation processes, in particular the operation request, acceptance and follow up. These tasks include physical, accounting, managerial or legal processes, and are tainted by their own specificities in terms of paths and issues depending on the operation dimensions. The main link with the FDM is the opportunity to learn about fraudster behaviour in order to better secure the operations for fraud deterrence or prevention (authentication processes, communication, regulation...): this opportunity is an important alternative to the fine tuning of the FDM itself and can be reflected by other automation innovations, excluded from this paper.

Process issues

The total *cost of fraud* is then the sum of the losses associated with criminal operations and false alerts, and investment to guard against them. This investment, technical or human, must remain lower than the expected gains, whether it is preserving margins or not losing customers. According to LexisNexis' "True Cost of Fraud Study", fraud costs in Financial Services from 2017 to 2018 have grown 9,3%, which is more than the revenue growth, in particular with the explosion of online and mobile channels. As the problem of task 1 can be recast as a learning problem, numerous approaches (Abdallah et al., 2016; Ryman-Tubb et al., 2018) have been developed to build models that optimize the precision of FDM to enhance or replace business filtering rules. However, the same study underlines that alerting solutions are still underperforming with too many false alerts: one-fourth of fraud costs remain dedicated to manual review, usually measured in Full Time Equivalent representing human intervention. In the meantime, these human tasks create the need for model explainability in order to treat each alert or understand globally the evolution of fraudsters' behaviour. In this context, minimizing false positives in the occurrence of the frauds goes hand in hand with the capacity to take into account the fraud specificities (evolving products on multiple channels, new behaviours and fraud vectors, human processes, legal and ethical issues,...) under profit constraint, and the use of Machine Learning to build the FDM raises several key questions for stakeholders and practitioners. Should the community learn the most explainable models to support tasks 2, 3 and 4 at the risk that they may be less accurate than the state-of-the-art blackbox model at task 1, or should the community learn the most accurate blackbox models before using post-hoc methods to interpret them? Clarifying the trade-off between predictive and descriptive accuracy (Murdoch et al., 2019; Rudin, 2019) is of major importance in order to provide pragmatic, short-term responses to the needs of banks and policy makers.

C. Modelling fraud detection and assessing performance

The general principle of an AI for detecting frauds is to either detect them because their characteristics differ from that of the majority of operations (i.e. non-fraudulent ones) or to learn a model of fraudulent operations from labeled operations (i.e. called *examples*). From an AI point of view, the first problem may be addressed using **unsupervised** learning or

anomaly detection, the second one using **supervised** machine learning. But some key issues, consistent with the constraints of the bank products and tasks described above, emerge from various surveys on machine learning for fraud detection. Before describing the SOTA of the methods used to support the automation of these tasks (see next section), we first detail how the quality assessment of an AI-based FDM from a business perspective is linked to performance measure of the associated machine learning tasks, in particular regarding five main issues: the relative rarity of fraud compared to normal operations, the importance of the cost of the fraudulent operations, the difficulty of labelling operations as fraudulent with certainty, the continuously changing nature of fraud, and finally the need of interpretability.

1) Frauds remain a “rare” event

Among transactions, bank accounts, exchanges or any other fraud targets, the vast majority of operations will be legitimate (non-fraudulent). Because fraud is so rare, data sets will be extremely biased in favour of non-fraud, which can seriously bias the models that are built from these data sets. The management of imbalanced classes generally requires data or algorithm transformation and the adjustment of precision measures. To illustrate the problem, let us consider that 3% of the transactions are fraudulent (positive). An algorithm that classifies by default all transactions as negatives (non fraudulent) will have an accuracy of 97% although it does not detect a single fraudulent transaction. To address this issue of *imbalanced data* there are various approaches. Confusion Matrix for example supports a more appropriate assessment of performances in an imbalanced setting. For a closer look at misclassification different metrics exist that combine the True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP) and False Negatives (FN), ignoring the True Negatives (TN) component that drowns out fraud information. These latter are mainly based on Precision (evaluation of the ratio of correct alerts) and Recall (evaluation of the number of fraudulent observations put on alert). Among other metrics, F1-Score, Geo-Mean or Precision-Recall curve are used to balance the trade-off between both Precision and Recall. The Receiver Operating Characteristic or ROC curves is also a very popular metric in the field of fraud analytics. A way to compare ROC curves is the AUC which computes the Area Under the ROC Curve (Davis and Goadrich, 2006). However, Precision-Recall curve and the AUC associated tends to generally better fit imbalanced data (Davis and Goadrich, 2006; Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015).

2) Fraud costs vary

Frauds account for only a small percentage of operations, and the cost of analysis of each alert can be significant, not to mention the customer risk of erroneously suspending normal operations. This leads to using metrics in Machine Learning that are cost-sensitive, i.e. that associate different weights to TP, FP, TN and FN examples. However, in the case of fraud detection, the situation can be much more complex because the fraud cost includes also the financial risk of each operation. Indeed, frequent but low amount frauds, in case of a long tailed distribution, may not be worth analyzing. Moreover, the fraud financial cost can be defined not only by the operation amount, but also by other criteria, such as a card limit reached after several low operations (Sahin et al., 2013) or a cash withdrawal amount after a

fraudulent cheque deposit. Machine Learning approaches rarely distinguish costs of the error according to these varying characteristics of the observations, whilst this aspect of misclassification can be critical to avoid drowning the signal of high impact frauds by the patterns of more frequent low impact frauds.

3) Frauds are difficult to label

To learn a model (be it a set of rules, or decision trees or a blackbox model) from examples, a dataset of examples of both fraudulent and non-fraudulent operations is required. However, because of the difficulty to assert the fraudulent status of operations, the label of the examples used in the associated machine learning task must be used with caution. Some of the operations might be labeled as “not fraudulent” although they are: the fraud will be revealed much later (see unanticipated fraud in Figure 3), or simply no one will ever know because the fraud has gone undetected. In Machine Learning, this issue of having examples that are wrongly labeled is known under the term of “noise”. From a practical point of view, it means that assessing the error of classification of a FDM will require some attention. When a model makes predictions on the label of unseen operations (e.g. labeling Positive the fraudulent and Negative the non-fraudulent), it is clear that, within the confusion matrix, the confidence on both the TN and FP is much lower than that of the TP and FN. It impacts the performance measure of the associated learning tasks.

4) Fraud patterns are quickly changing

Fraud management is a fight against professionals who actively seek to subvert the system at its weakest points. They imitate the characteristics and evolution of good customer behaviour to make fraudulent operations undetectable (Achituve et al., 2019; Choi and Lee, 2018; Dhankhad et al., 2018; Sadgali et al., 2019; SamanehSorournejad et al., 2016; Shah et al., 2019; Walke, 2019), and constantly test for loopholes in the fraud detection system. For the system, it means that the statistical properties of fraudulent and non-fraudulent operations evolve over a certain time. Most of the time, the system adaptation is processed manually: refinement of the rule is triggered when a specialist discovers a new type of fraud modus operandi in his bank or in a concurrent bank (change in input operations), or when he analyses the global FDM performance (global model monitoring). As legacy fraud detection systems often depend on fixed criteria or rules which hardly adapt to complex or new attack patterns (Ryman-Tubb et al., 2018), AI presents a true interest. However, for an automatic approach, in particular with a traditional supervised algorithm, recognizing old fraud behaviors that have appeared in the learning base is easy, but adapting to new behaviors as they occur is a real challenge: without retraining, the model performance declines rapidly. Furthermore, for voluminous or fast operations, such as credit card transactions, efficient automatic adaptation strategy is essential. A key question for the Bank is to balance the frequency of re-training the model with its cost while taking into account the speed and impact of changes in both the standard and fraudulent behavior.

5) Frauds need to be explained

After the alert has been raised, the investigation task (see Fig. 2 above) is required and a justification is needed to help the human in carrying out the investigation. This requirement explains why FDM models are much needed. The quality with which a model is able to explain its decision is referred to as “descriptive accuracy” and although more difficult to measure than “predictive accuracy” it represents a key assessment of the quality of the FDM. There are different ways to attain a high descriptive accuracy, either building interpretable models or develop post-hoc procedure that explains decisions from black-box models (Yu and Kumbier, 2020).

II- State of the art in fraud detection

In this section we propose a SOTA of methods that have been used in Machine Learning to address the specificities of Fraud Tasks and associated performance metrics: imbalance data, lack of labeled data, concept drift and the need for both accuracy and interpretability.

A. Dealing with imbalance data in fraud binary classification

As seen in section I-C-1, one of the specificities of fraud datasets is the strong class imbalance, the "fraud" class representing sometimes less than 1% of the whole dataset. Moreover, there is an overlap of both classes (see section I-C-4). These two phenomena therefore make classical supervised machine learning algorithms ineffective. The clue is to give more weight to the minority class either by modifying the data itself or the algorithm used through three possibilities: under-sampling negative observations, over-sampling positive observations, or hybrid methods allowing to combine under- and over-sampling (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Summary of solutions to deal with imbalanced data

Under-sampling consists in removing part of the observations from the majority class. The most basic method consists in removing elements of the majority class in a random way (Batista et al., 2004). Other methods try to better separate the classes to facilitate the learning of the models. This is the case of Near Miss and Condensed Nearest Neighbor -CNN- (Hart, 1968), selecting observations to keep. On the other hand, methods such as Tomek links (Tomek, 1976) and Edited Nearest Neighbors -ENN- (Wilson, 1972) try to select observations to remove. The latest methods combine both latter methods. For instance, One Sided Selection -OSS- (Kubat and Matwin, 1997) mixes CNN and Tomek links. The Neighborhood Cleaning rule method -NCL- (Laurikkala, 2001) improves OSS thanks to the ENN method. However, these methods are controversial and have poorer performance than oversampling methods (Batista et al., 2004).

Conversely, **over-sampling** aims to generate artificial observations of the minority class. The most basic method consists in duplicating some randomly chosen observations (Batista et al., 2004), but this method generates overfitting because of the duplicates. The Synthetic Minority Over-sampling TEchnique -SMOTE- method (Chawla et al., 2002) generates new observations. There are several methods which inherits from SMOTE such as BorderlineSMOTE, KMeansSMOTE, SVM SMOTE, or the well-known ADaptive SYNthetic -ADASYN- (He et al., 2008). As recommended, hybriding methods can combine both over-sampling and under-sampling (Batista et al., 2004).

On the other hand, **algorithm modification** consists in giving more weight to the minority. Firstly, as explained in I-C, it is crucial to adapt performance metrics in order to optimize parameters and assess the validity of the algorithm taking into account the imbalancing of the class. Furthermore, some algorithms (mainly tree structures) take into account the imbalancing of the classes as for example SMOTE Boost (Chawla et al., 2003), MetaCost (Domingos, 2002) and AdaCost (Fan et al., 1999). Another approach is to give more weight to fraudulent observations than to normal observations. This changes the cost function and it is named cost-sensitive learning (Elkan, 2001). The cost of misclassifying fraudulent observations is here globally modified. Hence it can't respond to the issue of long-tailed costs (see I-C-2) linked to the amount of the operation (local modification of the cost), should it be simple or combined to other factors. One possible solution is to under-sample the dataset thanks to business knowledge, such as: *"In general, isolated fraudulent contactless payments of less than 10€ are not worth treating"*. This business under-sampling allows us to only focus detection on costly frauds.

When dealing with fraud data, using data level balancing techniques, like SMOTE, tends to be preferred instead of modifying the algorithm (Brennan and Hofmann, 2012; Dal Pozzolo et al., 2014).

B. Dealing with the lack of fully trusted labels

Beyond the limits of supervised models on imbalance data, they prove to be even less efficient on poorly labelled phenomena. Indeed, a characteristic of successful fraud is that it

has gone unnoticed in history. This means that real fraud datasets often have frauds among the "non-fraudulent" observations. It is therefore recommended, in the case of not fully trusted labelled data, to use **anomaly detection** methods that are semi-supervised or unsupervised. Figure 4 presents the main algorithms.

Figure 4: Summary of anomaly detection methods

Semi-supervised algorithms are trained on non-fraudulent observations and then detect abnormal, and therefore potentially fraudulent observations, during the test phase. Among them, the best known is One-class SVM (Schölkopf et al., 2001). With the advent of neural networks, many neural approaches to semi-supervised learning, such as models based on auto-encoders (Aggarwal, 2017; Hawkins et al., 2002), have been developed for fraud detection.

Several categories of **unsupervised methods** coexist. Most methods are linked to the neighbourhood of the observations, and can be distance-based, such as k-nearest neighbours (Knorr and Ng, 1998; Ramaswamy et al., 2000), or density-based, attempting to identify isolated points as anomalies. Among density-based methods, Local Outlier Factor -LOF- (Breunig et al., 2000) is a local method which was improved to Connectivity-based Outlier Factor -COF- (Tang et al., 2002), and Isolation Forest (Liu et al., 2012) uses tree algorithms. Most recent methods are based on other clustering methods aiming to detect anomalies, such as Cluster-Based Local Outlier Factor -CBLOF- (He et al., 2003) or Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise -DBSCAN algorithm- (Campello et al., 2015). Finally, some well-known categories of unsupervised methods are also used for anomaly detection, including former methods using statistical tests (Rousseeuw and Driessen, 1999) or the Robust Principal Component Analysis -r-PCA- (Candès et al., 2011), based on dimension reduction.

According to surveys (Kou et al., 2004), anomaly or outlier detection was one of the main techniques used in credit card fraud detection in 2004 and it was still the case in 2016 (Abdallah et al., 2016). This can be explained by the fact that this kind of algorithm can easily handle not only the lack of trusted labels, but also partly answer to the problem of constant fraud evolution : a so-called concept drift problem.

C. Dealing with the drifting

As fraudsters adapt their behaviour according to the product and control techniques evolution, the fraud patterns change: this phenomenon, called **concept drift**, appears when the underlying distribution of target concept depends on *hidden contexts* (Widmer and Kubat, 1996), and results in the need to re-train the model.

Besides anomaly detection described above and manual adaptations through operations or model analysis, seen in section I-C-4, partly dealing with the phenomenon, the classifier in supervised models can be continuously updated when new fraudulent operations become available, for example through regular relearning on a sliding window (Dal Pozzolo et al., 2015). For gradually drifting environments, such as bank cheque operations, it is possible then to choose a specific frequency or threshold to re-train the model. It is named **offline** learning mode (Gama et al., 2014). However, in contexts of risk of abrupt changes or voluminous and veloce operations, such as for credit card transactions, new stakes arise: adapt to concept drift, be robust to noise and able to treat recurring contexts (Tsybmal, 2004). It is known as stream data and it involves developing **online** learning solutions (Gama et al., 2014). All the above re-learning modes are illustrated in Figure 5 before developing this last technique.

		Re-training mode	
Operator		analysing input operations	monitoring globally model outcomes
	After a rare fraud event: new fraud behaviour detected by expert teams		Decrease of global performances essentially seen through the reporting
	Change of distribution of one(s) variables detected <i>online learning</i>		Re-training planned on a certain frequency or at a certain threshold <i>offline learning</i>

Figure 5: Procedures handling the concept drift

The easiest way to deal with online learning is to process incremental models. However, those methods, such as Hoeffding trees (Domingos and Hulten, 2000), require adapting the model for each new example. In order to use less calculation memory and time, several

methods propose to work on a window containing the most recent examples, of fixed or adaptive size, as in FLORA2 (Widmer and Kubat, 1996).

To decide whether to learn the model again or not, it is necessary to **detect drifts**. A lot of statistical tests consist in comparing the statistical distributions such as CUmulative SUM -CUSUM- (Bissell, 1986) inspired by Sequential Probability Ratio Test -SPRT- or former methods such as Shiryaev-Roberts test (Roberts, 1966; Shiryaev, 1961). More recent models tend to adapt the size of window to compare distributions, ADWIN is one of these examples (Bifet and Gavaldà, 2007). Afterwards, when the concept drift has been detected, there are several possibilities: learn again the model on complete historical data or on new observations, or use an old context model as in FLORA3 (Widmer and Kubat, 1996).

This subject is at stake as more and more areas requisite to work with stream data, and several solutions combining online learning and drift detection have been generally developed (Gama et al., 2014; Lu et al., 2018; Webb et al., 2016; Žliobaitė, 2010; Žliobaitė et al., 2016) and adapted to fraud detection (Dal Pozzolo et al., 2015, 2014).

D. Dealing with the interpretability vs. accuracy tradeoff

As the three latter parts deal with analytical constraints, the last operational requirement, described in section 1-C-5, is still unresolved: practitioners need interpretable results to act. We identify 3 main approaches in this direction, as shown in Figure 6: intrinsically interpretable models, and post hoc specific or agnostic methods.

Figure 6: Summary of algorithms for interpretability

Intrinsically interpretable models, such as linear regression, logistic regression, decision trees or combinations of business decision rules, are generally not accurate enough for tasks such as fraud detection that have high financial stakes. We are facing the Interpretability-Accuracy trade-off (Shukla and Tripathi, 2011). Some think that we should boost interpretable models to gain accuracy (Rudin, 2019) while others prefer to use state of the art black-box models and then apply post hoc interpretability methods to provide explanations of how they work or their results.

Among these methods, some, called **model-specific**, are specific to a type of model. Examples of such methods when dealing with sets of decision trees are the Classification Aggregation Table scan -CAT scan- (Rao and Potts, 1997) or the Feature Importance Permutation metric (Breiman, 2001). For Support Vector Machines -SVM-, Nomograms (Jakulin et al., 2005) were a new visualization approach. Finally, for neural networks, known for better performances on some problems but also for their interpretation complexity, several specific techniques have been developed such as Deep Learning Important Features -DeepLIFT- (Shrikumar et al., 2017) or Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (Bach et al., 2015). The main disadvantage of the latter is that their use is restricted to a single type of model and it is therefore complicated to compare performances and explanations of several different models.

To counter this disadvantage, **model-agnostic** methods can be used. They can be macro (or global) in order to obtain an overall view of the model to understand it in its entirety, or finer (or local) to study a particular case or observation.

As **visualization** is one of the most useful tools for interpreting models, visual interpretation approaches have been implemented. The main ones are Partial Dependence Plot -PDP curves- (Friedman, 2001) and Accumulated Local Effect plots -ALE curves- (Apley and Zhu, 2019) for macro approaches and Individual Conditional Expectation curves -ICE- (Goldstein et al., 2014) for local approaches. These methods reveal the effect of a variable within a model. In order to better choose which variables to plot, it is necessary to know which variables have the greatest influence on the prediction and are therefore the most important for the model. For this, the Model Reliance measure (Fisher et al., 2018) is the agnostic version of Permutation Feature Importance measure (Breiman, 2001). Moreover, if variables interact with each other in a model, visualizing their effects separately is not enough. Methods, such as Interaction Strength (Friedman and Popescu, 2008) or Variable Interaction Networks -VIN- (Hooker, 2004) allow to analyze and interpret the effects of interactions between variables.

Another classical technique of interpretation is to use following a black box model another more interpretable model. These are the **surrogate** models, also known as approximation models or metamodels. The best known local surrogate models are Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanation -LIME- (Ribeiro et al., 2016), Model-Agnostic Hierarchical Explanations -MAHE- (Tsang et al., 2018) and SHapley Additive exPlanations -SHAP- (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) as well as all its derivatives: KernelSHAP, SHAP features importances, SHAP summary plot and SHAP dependence plots (Lundberg et al., 2019).

III- Experimentation

The SOTA shed some light on a race for the best technology between black-box machine learning models improved by post-hoc interpretation and intrinsic interpretable models boosted to gain accuracy, and the mains analytical streams to deal with other specificities of fraud detection. We experimentally illustrate the differences between these two approaches under operational constraints in the framework of a European project financed by the ERDF,

called Cerberus, where two private AI actors had to cooperate to propose innovative solutions for fraud management. The project resulted in the deployment of two solutions, closely related to their application characteristics.

First, an anti-fraud software, carried by the publisher Bleckwen, is developed for instant cash transfer fraud, characterized by high operation frequencies and limited human involvement. This software is based on the improvement of a blackbox scoring model, resulting in a fraud probability score, completed with a local interpretative overlay: all operations over a given optimal threshold are suspended and have to be investigated.

The second solution is an adaptation of the intrinsic interpretable analysis methods based on the Q-Finder algorithm with proven results in medicine (Amrane et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2019), to the world of fraud by consulting firm Quinten. This method generates automatically from historical data optimized business decision rules, as limited combinations of patterns, and classifies the new operations into two categories (fraud or not) as a binary alert. It allows to optimize cheque fraud management, which is characterized by lower volumes and slower human processes (instant operation is not needed as customers accept a several hours delay for this operation). In this second context, an operational combination of both of models (rules generation and fraud scoring) is implemented to explore the benefit of a hybrid approach of the FDM, as shown in Figure 7. In this section, we present the performance and deployment issues of this promising hybridization.

Figure 7: Interpretability vs accuracy trade-off, inspired by Yang et al., 2019

Since, in the banking sector, interpretability is necessary for the action, and fraud experts analyse easily limited fraud factors, the hybrid method is based on business rules that it completes or replaces. For this, Quinten's method using the Q-Finder algorithm generates a large number of intersected rules to detect the phenomenon of costly fraud. The advantages are that the coverage of fraud by the rules is generally very good and that the variables that intervene in each rule are co-constructed through features engineering with the business experts to ensure easy interpretability. Moreover, all operations under a certain business-defined amount were excluded at the pre-processing stage as not worth investigating: this treatment avoids drawing the characteristics of heavy frauds by those of frequent frauds, and, simultaneously, generates an undersampling of non-fraudulent operations. However, at this stage the approach generates a set of rules with too many false positives, which can lead to customer dissatisfaction and to an inability to deal with all the alerts by the anti-fraud department. Thus, an optimal combination of rules is created in order to reduce the number of false positives and maintain good coverage: for this, an F-beta score is used with e.g. beta equal to 3 to give more weight to the recall. The number of selected rules is then limited to the available human resources to treat the alerts. At this point, the interpretability and the accuracy are guaranteed by an optimized intrinsic interpretative model under cost constraint.

This rule generation model is hybridized in a second step with a blackbox score model developed in parallel on all the operations. This scoring model is intended to be applied after the rules, so that all alerts can be prioritized by the score. This prioritization speeds up the work of the fraud experts without deteriorating the intelligible explanation of the fraud. If the number of alerts punctually creates an investigative workload that is even less than the capacity of the dedicated human resources, the set of rules can be completed with an additional rule corresponding to the operations with a score over a very high threshold: in this case, only this part of alerts, as a complementary "scoring rule", is harder to interpret, but the coverage of the fraud is enhanced for available human resources.

Furthermore, as one of the main characteristics of fraud is the concept drift, the rules may no longer be accurate after a certain time of changes in fraudsters behaviour. To get around this problem, the blackbox model is enhanced with online-learning, thus the addition of a rule based on the score model threshold maintains the efficiency of the FDM by detecting new fraudster behaviours. The majority of the operations in alert will then have an explanation given by the business rules, the others will correspond to new fraud techniques not learned yet by the rules. These alerts will require more investigation time from the fraud experts because they will not have a business explanation that can be quickly understood. When the number of alerts not explained by the business rules starts to be too high, new optimized rules have to be learned from on the recent data: this statistico-economic equilibrium is closely followed as part of the monitoring task. A new business investigation will help to understand where these new frauds come from thanks to the new rules created, optimize fraud deterrence and prevention if possible, and finetune the FDM. During all the lifecycle, only exceptional frauds would have passed under the radar: these outliers did not appear to be economically pertinent to detect.

In order to illustrate statistically this hybrid method, here are some synthetic results obtained using data from Quinten's partner about cheques' frauds. For reasons of confidentiality, only the numbers of fraud cases detected will be reported, although the amounts were part of the analysis. On Figure 8, we can see that most of the frauds detected each month by a score with a threshold at 50% are also detected by the rules, so the use of interpretable models can be easily privileged for operational reasons: prioritize by the scoring model and explained by the rules. Moreover, the combination of the two models gives better results while adding only a limited number of alerts, as shown on Figure 9. Indeed, the available fraud experts can not handle more than 30 daily alerts. In this example, the last month's fraud are not observed for the moment: the rules are still functional alone.

Figure 8: Number of true fraud cases detected over 1 year

Figure 9: Average number of alerts (TP + FP) per day over 1 year

This hybridization answers key issues of each task of fraud management mentioned in the section I-B, as resumed in Figure 10, and was judged as immediately operational and very promising by the first banking partners. It is being deployed in association with two user interfaces designed for the collaborative investigation and the monitoring tasks. If further model optimization seem tempting, such as the interpretative overlaying model on the “score rule” alerts or a complementary outlier model for new fraud trends, other considerations appear as much more pragmatic, such as fraud perimeter enlargement, an automatic link to the bank accountability in order to accelerate the action task (treatment of the most suspicious operations and release of the less suspicious suspended operations), or simply data skills transfer to fraud experts. Under investment constraints, these pragmatic considerations remind that the “performance” of such AI devices are far from being solely statistical.

	Rules	Score
Task 1 Alerting	Statistically optimized set of business rules for automatized alerting	« Scoring Rule » completing the set without overcharging the number of alerts
Task 2 Investigation	Interpretability of each alert through a combination of explicit fraud patterns for each rule	Priorization of alerts by fraud score in order to gain in investigation productivity
Task 3 Action	Concentration of the model on heavy frauds only. Concession to get through exceptional frauds that are too costly to deal with.	
	Justification for action facilitated by interpretability	Acceleration for the more and the less suspected alerts
Task 4 Monitoring	Generation of knowledge on new fraudsters' behaviours and, when needed, of optimized rules	Online-learning model adapting to the fraudsters' behaviour

Figure 10: Synthesis of the answers of the hybrid FDM to fraud management task issues

Conclusion

Humans are in the loop of many business processes in banking, as is fraud detection. Just as the task of classifying a tumor is only one aspect of a dermatologist's work, identifying a potential fraud is only one step in a more complex fraud management process. Human processes of evaluation and action against the fraudster makes it difficult to simply compare machine learning algorithms on their performance or explanatory power outside of their use by the practitioner. In the field of fraud detection, although rule-based approaches remain the standard in banks, data-based rule learning approaches can be used to reach much better performance. Furthermore, some tasks of the fraud management can be optimized with blackbox models, as soon as an explanation of the decision is not required for the investigation or for a legal action against the fraudster. While the question of which approach

will give the best answer is still open, we showed on a practical example that it is possible in the meantime to hybridize both approaches to develop improved solutions for the complete fraud management process.

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